

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF INTRAPRENEURSHIP IN THE IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON INNOVATION PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

In Today's rapidly changing environment, organizations are compelled to keep up with technological advancements and evolving business practices, pressuring them to attain and implement novel approaches quickly. This study investigates the relationship between organizational culture and innovation performance, emphasizing the mediating role of intrapreneurship in organizations. The research was conducted among mid-level and senior managers, as well as white-collar employees of a large-scale enterprise operating in Kayseri, Turkey, using the survey technique. A total of 153 survey responses were analyzed using SPSS. Based on mean, standard deviation, correlations between variables, and the results of regression analysis for hypotheses, it can be stated that organizational culture impacts intrapreneurial behaviors and innovation performance. Furthermore, the analyses indicate that intrapreneurship plays a mediating role in the influence of organizational culture on innovation performance.

Keywords: *Intrapreneurship, Organizational Culture, Innovation Performance*

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ÖRGÜT KÜLTÜRÜNÜN İNOVASYON PERFORMANSINA ETKİSİNDE İÇ GİRİŞİMCİLİĞİN ARACI ROLÜ

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ÖZ

Günümüzde bosta değişen teknolojilerin ve iş yapış şekillerinin örgütlerin üzerinde yaptığı baskı örgütleri değişen hızla ayak uydurmaya zorunlu kılmakla birlikte yeniyi daha çabuk elde etme ve faaliyetlerine yansıtma konusunda baskı kurmaktadır. Bu çalışmada örgüt kültürü ve inovasyon performansı arasındaki ilişki incelenmiş ve bu ilişkide iç girişimciliğin aracılık rolü üstlenip üstlenmediği tespit edilmeye çalışılmıştır. Araştırma Kayseri’de faaliyet göstermekte olan büyük ölçekli bir işletmenin orta ve üst düzey yöneticileri ile beyaz yakalı çalışanları üzerinde yapılmış, anket tekniği kullanılmış ve 153 anket değerlendirmeye tabi tutulmuştur. Veriler SPSS ortamında analiz edilmiştir. Değişkenlere ilişkin ortalama, standart sapma ve değişkenler arasındaki korelasyonlar ve Hipotezlere ilişkin regresyon analizi sonuçlarına dayanarak örgüt kültürünün örgüt içindeki iç girişimcilik davranışlarında ve inovasyon performansı üzerinde etkisi olduğu söylemek mümkündür. Bunun yanında analizler örgüt kültürünün inovasyon performansı üzerine etkisinde iç girişimciliğin aracılık rolü üstlendiğine işaret etmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İç girişimcilik, Örgüt Kültürü, İnovasyon Performansı

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1. INTRODUCTION

Culture is generally regarded as a set of assumptions that shapes the emotions, thoughts, and perceptions shared within a community and provides a framework for various perspectives on the world (Schein, 1996). In terms of encompassing assumptions related to work, organizational culture is a concept that directly influences an organization's outcomes. The insights an employee forms about the organization will also directly impact their contribution. For employees to exhibit innovative behaviours that contribute to the organization and integrate them, they must believe that the organizational culture supports such behaviour. A strong organizational culture distinguishes an organization from others and influences how the organization and its members function (Robbins, 1999). Organizational culture represents the understanding within an organization about how work should be performed, thus directly affecting employee performance. Particularly, how innovation is received within an organization influences employees' capacity to access new knowledge, bring it into the organization, transform it, and utilize it as valuable knowledge. Innovation is crucial for organizations to sustain themselves in a rapidly changing world. Innovation performance entails producing products or transforming selected ideas into commercially viable products and services. The creation of innovation by employees within the organization will enhance innovation performance. However, this is achievable only through the encouragement of employees in this regard.

Entrepreneurship involves identifying and evaluating opportunities that are not readily apparent to others, converting them into economic concepts, and undertaking the associated risks. An important aspect here is for the entrepreneur to have a valuable and economically productive idea that can be converted into a tangible product by effectively combining resources, competencies, skills, and human capital. In this context, the entrepreneur undertakes the risk of successful and unsuccessful outcomes associated with the process. The entrepreneur taking on this risk amalgamates value, effort, and other factors to create value or to elevate lower-value tasks to a higher value. Schumpeter emphasized the significance of the relationship between innovation and entrepreneurship. According to Schumpeter, the entrepreneur is the source of creative destruction, a driver of change. An entrepreneur introduces a new product or method to the market, creating a new market or even establishing a new industry (Ohyama et al., 2009). Hence, entrepreneurs take risks, show initiative, and can organize resources to add value.

The effects of economic developments and globalization in the latter half of the 20th century compel businesses to sustain themselves on shifting grounds, and due to the rapid dissemination of information, they face pressure to acquire innovations more swiftly. In such a structure, businesses can only thrive if they adapt to technology, customer demands, and changing conditions. This can only be achieved through the integration of innovation. Entrepreneurship is often associated with the concept of innovation within its definition. Value creation (Vesper, 1990; Hisrich, 1986) and innovation (Schumpeter, 1934; Vesper, 1990; Sharma & Chrisman, 1999; Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2007) are central features of entrepreneurship. Intrapreneurship, also referred to as corporate entrepreneurship, serves to keep these two factors vibrant within organizations. Intrapreneurship involves employees utilizing their creativity to establish new activities within the organization. In this context, developing an organizational culture that supports innovation within the organization is crucial. Organizational culture has a direct impact on all employees. This influence can either facilitate the transformation of information into innovative ideas that an employee can utilize for the organization or serve as a hindrance. Whether intrapreneurship plays a mediating role in this context constitutes the research objective.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study section introduces the concepts of organizational culture, innovation performance, and intrapreneurship and provides a literature review.

2.1. Organizational Culture

Culture is considered the most abstract concept influencing human behaviour (McCort & Malhotra, 1993). While different definitions have been proposed, the most common definition of organizational culture is provided by Lundy and Cowling (1996). They assert that organizational culture constitutes the naturally occurring activities within an organization. In organizational behaviour, organizational culture is defined as "a set of values and beliefs that provide norms for both internal insights into organizational functioning and

employee behaviour" (Deshpande & Webster, 1989). Alternatively, Schein (1992) defines organizational culture as the set of fundamental assumptions that a specific group invents, discovers, or develops to solve problems of adaptation and internal integration while learning to think and perceive in a way shared among group members. These assumptions can be transmitted to new members as a way of thinking and perceiving.

From another perspective, organizational culture can be defined as the values, norms, meanings, beliefs, and symbolic expressions formed from mutual interactions and communications among the employees of an organization (Özdemir & Sönmez, 2018). For an organization to sustain itself and succeed, it must possess strong values and beliefs, including all policies and actions (Varol, 1989). These values and beliefs form the foundation of organizational culture. The uniqueness and value of each organization's culture and its covert and implicit structure make it difficult for competitors to imitate, thereby providing a sustainable competitive advantage (Coyne, 1986). Empirical and theoretical studies on organizational innovation emphasize the determining role of organizational culture on innovation performance (Robertson & Wind, 1980; Coyne, 1986; Branen, 1991; Ahmed, 1998; Herbig & Dunphy, 1998). Creating an organizational culture that supports innovation involves establishing an environment that maintains employees' overall well-being, serves them in their career paths, and provides a high-quality work life. It is important to create an environment that empowers and encourages employee participation. Innovation is fundamentally transforming certain ideas and thoughts into commercializable outputs. It is important to channel employees' creative abilities into this transformation process. Therefore, fostering a culture encouraging employees and their creativity will facilitate innovation (Mumford, 2000).

Innovative attitudes within organizations can develop through the socialization process. Firstly, the organisation's socialisation process teaches employees how to behave toward each other. In addition, the organization's structure, policies, procedures, and management style are influenced by the "values, beliefs, and assumptions" generated by organizational culture (Martins & Terblanche, 2003). Hence, organizational culture can minimize restrictions that inhibit individual creativity (Angle, 1988; Barney & Grifn, 1992) and promote innovation (Hartmann, 2006). Culture is also important in instilling the organization's innovation philosophy among employees. Different values within the culture encourage innovation within the organization. For instance, creativity and initiative (Wallach, 1983; Schneider et al., 1994; Claver et al., 1998; McLean, 2005; Jamrog et al., 2006), entrepreneurial mindset (McLean, 2005), freedom and autonomy (Ahmed, 1998; Martins & Terblanche, 2003; McLean, 2005; Jamrog et al., 2006), risk-taking (Wallach, 1983; Claver et al., 1998; Martins & Terblanche, 2003), teamwork (Arad et al., 1997; Martins & Terblanche, 2003; McLean, 2005; Jamrog et al., 2006), marketing orientation, and flexibility (Arad et al., 1997; Martins & Terblanche, 2003).

Creativity refers to the emergence of new and substantially unprecedented ideas, and innovation involves the commercialized applications of these creative ideas (Mumford, 2000). For this reason, a business requires a culture that supports the processes related to creative idea development and the processes involving the selection, evaluation, and implementation of ideas. A culture that supports innovation in businesses should encourage employees to engage in creative thinking and experimentation on the one hand (Shattow, 1996). On the other hand, it should encourage them to seek new ways to overcome challenges and explore their ideas, regardless of their value or outcome (Miron et al., 2004). Supporting this notion, Sebora and Theerapatvong (2010) found that internal managers supported by the organizational environment were more prone to taking risks, were more innovative, and exhibited more proactive behaviour.

In conclusion, an organizational climate where the organization's intrapreneurs are unafraid of making mistakes, openly express their opinions, and are not penalized will encourage them to engage in innovations that will propel the organization forward.

2.2. Innovation

The term "innovation" is derived from the Latin word "innovare," meaning renewal (Narayanan, 2001, p. 67). The OECD defines innovation as the "implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service) or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization, or external relations" (2005). Despite various definitions, the most widely accepted definition is found in the Oslo Manual (2005), which states that "innovation involves the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization, or external relations."

Adams et al. (2006) argue that there cannot be a single definition of innovation, yet it is evident that diverse definitions converge around key attributes. Accordingly, innovation can refer to the initial, early, or novel utilization of products, ideas, services, production processes, or practices by an organization (Becker & Whisler, 1967; Rothman et al., 1976; Rogers, 1983; Rickards, 1985; Udwardia, 1990; Cumming, 1998; Flynn et al., 2003; Sami, 2003; Velmurugan et al., 2013). Innovation involves entering new or different markets (Schumpeter, 1934; Parthasarathy & Hammond, 2002; Van de Vrande et al., 2009), adding novelty or modifications to existing products, services, or processes (Damanpour & Evan, 1984; Udwardia, 1990; Pretorius et al., 2005; Tutar et al., 2007; Demir & Demir, 2015).

In developing innovation-related strategies, organizations aim to achieve various objectives, including surpassing competitors in growth and profit (Crespell & Hansen, 2008), expanding into new markets, sustaining growth, preserving current revenues (Van de Vrande et al., 2009), maintaining competitive advantage (Tushman & Anderson, 1986; Cui et al., 2006), and ultimately achieving superior outcomes in all respects. Organizations accomplishing these objectives through innovation reduce their dependence on other countries and businesses, fostering sustainability (Demir & Demir, 2015). As such, innovation practices adopted by organizations, from developing new products, technologies, and designs to promoting, marketing, and holistic management, will contribute to businesses through a sustainable innovation strategy (Ventura & Soyer, 2016).

With changing environmental conditions and developments in information technologies (Yılmaz et al. 2017), one of the most foremost innovation objectives for businesses has been to gain competitive advantage. With innovation strategies, businesses can not only achieve market leadership but also accomplish other objectives. Beyond the benefits enumerated earlier, innovation activities also yield advantages in fulfilling customer desires and needs, fostering loyalty and increased customer satisfaction, and generating new business opportunities and dynamic, creative work environments (Davis & Moe, 1997). Recent research has extensively debated the impact of various innovation types in an organizational context on businesses' long-term survival, performance, and profitability (Banbury & Mitchell, 1995; McGrath et al., 1996; Daneels, 2002).

2.2.1. Innovation Performance

In addition to the manifold benefits that innovation processes provide to organizations, it is essential to recognize that the outcomes of these processes will vary for each organization and be managed differently. Innovation strategies are influenced in diverse ways by organizational characteristics (Hameed & Counsell, 2014; Çetin & Gedik, 2017), competitive and market conditions, knowledge factors, cost factors, and institutional factors (Oslo Manual, 2005; Çalçıner & Baç, 2007; Romero & Martínez-Roman, 2012). Encountering barriers, resistance, and difficulties during the idea generation, implementation, and commercialization phases is plausible. Consequently, how managers manage the innovation process will significantly impact its success, referred to as innovation performance (Taşgıt & Torun, 2016).

Increasingly, the innovation process is recognized as being bifurcated into two fundamental stages, with consensus among scholars. The initial stage encompasses the production of products; the second stage involves converting selected ideas into commercialised products and services (Adams & Hublikar, 2010; Cooper & Edgett, 2012). Innovation performance denotes the degree of fulfilment of these two stages (Wang & Ahmed, 2004). This concept is also understood as the commercial dimension of the return of new products, processes, and ideas to the business (Ertuğ & Bülbül, 2015).

Measuring the innovation performance of businesses not only showcases the outputs of prior innovation activities but can also be perceived as a prerequisite for implementing novel innovation activities. Consequently, innovation performance indicators enable organizations to comprehend their current standing in innovation, whether successful or unsuccessful (Taşgıt & Torun, 2016). Innovation performance can embody increased profit margins, market share growth, competitive advantage, and societal value and prestige contributions by firms. Just as there is a lack of consensus regarding the definition of innovation in the literature, there is also a dearth of unanimity concerning measuring innovation performance. Innovation measurement studies have been conducted primarily by institutions such as the European Commission and the OECD.

Additionally, institutions like the World Bank, INSEAD, and the Fraunhofer Institute have conducted innovation survey applications and system development studies to measure innovation performance

(Karaata, 2012). The OECD relies on three criteria when measuring innovation performance: patents, licenses, and R&D expenditures. Moreover, Hoonsopon and Ruenrom (2012) employ market and financial indicators, while Alegre and Chiva (2013) divide innovation performance into effectiveness and efficiency. Ledwith and O'Dwyer (2009) include customer, product, and timing indicators alongside market and financial indicators. Tanev (2005) measures innovation performance through the number of technological products introduced to the market, the number of technological production processes, and the number of implemented technological services and patents. Hu (2003) focuses on the indicators of innovation and patent numbers. Zehir and Özşahin (2008) assess innovation performance based on how the business market responds to changes and innovations in products, the rate of introducing new products and services in the past five years, and whether the business is ahead in the market when introducing new products or services. Lastly, Subramaniam and Yount (2005) anchor their assessment on patents, licenses, and R&D expenditures. In this study, by taking into account the divergent perspectives encompassed in the literature on innovation performance measurement, a scale consisting of 15 items and open-ended questions that multiple authors have used was translated into Turkish and used.

Factors influence the innovation performance of organizations in their internal and external environments. Rabor et al. (2011) categorize these factors into environmental factors, internal factors, firm strategic capabilities, and production, marketing, and R&D activities. One of the internal factors is organizational culture. While innovation initiatives and their outcomes are generally perceived as the work of the R&D department (Capon et al., 1992; Harrison, 1997; Koen & Kohli, 1998), and despite the close relationship between innovation performance and these initiatives (Sirilli & Evangelista, 1998), the propagation of an innovation philosophy throughout the organization's culture would yield more sustainable results. In cultures where all employees other than R&D departments freely express their ideas and these ideas are valued, an increase in innovation performance is expected (Claver et al., 1998).

2.3. Intrapreneurship

The term "entrepreneurship" was first introduced by Say and is derived from the French word "entrepreneur" (Top, 2012:4). According to Say, entrepreneurship was a concept that changed the existing economic order (Topkaya, 2013). From the perspective of renowned economist Schumpeter (1934), entrepreneurship is converting innovative ideas into new products, services, or ventures by taking risks to exploit market opportunities. The essence of Schumpeter's definition of entrepreneurship revolves around innovation. According to Schumpeter, an entrepreneur is an individual who discovers new raw materials and supply sources, develops new products (goods or services) and processes, identifies new markets, or creates new organizational structures, thus introducing new combinations to businesses and disrupting the existing economic order (Ağca and Kandemir, 2008:214).

Intrapreneurship, a distinct form of entrepreneurial activity, bears many similarities to entrepreneurship. However, intrapreneurship occurs within the organization. Pinchot defines an internal entrepreneur as an individual within a company responsible for implementing any business idea (Pinchot, 1985:15).

Intrapreneurship can be defined as creating new ventures within an established organization (Antoncic and Hisrich, 2001). In addition to creating new ventures within existing organizations, it involves generating new products, processes, technologies, and methods (Damanpour, 1996; Burgelman and Rosenblom, 1997; Tushman and Anderson, 1997), establishing autonomous or semi-autonomous ventures (Schollhammer, 1981; Zahra, 1991; Sharma and Chrisman, 1991), innovating production processes and techniques (Schollhammer, 1981; Knight, 1997; Zahra, 1993; Tushman and Anderson, 1997), taking initiative within the organization or embarking on initial ventures (Covin and Slevin, 1991; Lumpkin, 1998), and ultimately exhibiting autonomy in bringing ideas to fruition.

Zahra (1991:260) equates intrapreneurship with corporate entrepreneurship, using the same concept in the same sense. Corporate entrepreneurship refers to "formal or informal activities at the organizational, departmental, functional, and project levels aimed at creating new ventures through innovations in products, processes, and market development to enhance the competitive position and financial performance of an existing organization." In essence, intrapreneurship is defined as a process that fosters organizational renewal and encourages an entrepreneurial spirit within the organization, creating new ventures to improve organizational profitability and enhance competitive power (Gürel, 2012).

Sathe (1989) defines intrapreneurship as a process of organizational renewal with two distinct dimensions. The first dimension involves creating a 'new business' through entrepreneurial and market development approaches by creating new products, processes, or technologies. The second dimension involves concretizing innovative activities that enhance a firm's capacity for competition and risk-taking (Kuratko et al., 2002:254; Zahra, 2000:253; Kuratko, 2000:19). Intrapreneurship can potentially impact economies by contributing to productivity gains, uncovering best practices, creating new industries, and elevating business enterprises to internationally competitive levels (Ağca and Yörük, 2006).

The imperative of possessing entrepreneurial thinking to respond to environmental changes has added a new dimension to the concept of entrepreneurship (Naktiyok and Kök, 2006: 78). Today, entrepreneurship encompasses both starting new ventures and seeking opportunities, effecting change, and fostering innovation and creativity within existing organizations (Onay and Çavuşoğlu, 2010). Most researchers consider creativity and innovation to be the focal points of intrapreneurship. Internal entrepreneurs are individuals within an organization who engage in innovation and idea-generation activities. Knight (1967) emphasizes that the most significant outcome of intrapreneurship activities is the creation of new products and services. This perspective has led to the implicit or explicit endorsement of supporting and developing internal entrepreneurs in the literature (de Chambeau and Mackenzie, 1986; Adams et al., 1988; Ellis and Taylor, 1988; Block and MacMillan, 1993; Brazeal, 1993; Bowman, 1999; Gapp and Fisher, 2007). With increasing competition, businesses require employees who positively impact their strategies, find more creative working methods, and rapidly adapt to changing conditions (Peters and Waterman, 1982). These employees are the internal entrepreneurs within the organization. Internal entrepreneurs differentiate the organizational climate by promoting innovation and triggering significant changes (Alt and Craig, 2016), ultimately reflecting on organizational performance. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that intrapreneurship, particularly its impact on innovation performance, could be substantial.

3. METHOD

3.1. Research Objectives and Hypotheses

This study aims to examine the relationship between organizational culture and innovation performance while elucidating the mediating role of intrapreneurship within this relationship. In this context, the hypotheses and research model of the study are outlined below:

H1: Organizational culture significantly influences innovation performance.

H2: Organizational culture significantly influences intrapreneurship.

H3: Intrapreneurship significantly influences innovation performance.

H4: The mediating role of intrapreneurship is significant in the relationship between organizational culture and innovation performance.

Figure 1. Research Model

3.2. Research Method and Sample

The data utilized in this study were collected through surveys administered to middle and upper-level managers and white-collar employees of a large-scale business operating in Kayseri. Prior permission was obtained to administer the survey form that was prepared in alignment with the research objectives. The data were collected voluntarily, and participants were invited to respond to the survey form. The opinions

of participants were collected through face-to-face interviews. After identifying and correcting incomplete and erroneous coding, 153 out of 250 distributed surveys were considered for analysis. The survey employed a Five-Point Likert scale (1: Strongly Disagree, 5: Strongly Agree; 1= Not Important at All, 5= Very Important) as its basis.

To ensure the reliability of the obtained data, skewness and kurtosis values were examined to determine whether the data exhibited a normal distribution. A four-stage regression analysis, as recommended by Baron and Kenny (1986), was conducted to test the research model. According to this method, four conditions must be met to establish the presence of a mediation effect (Baron and Kenny, 1986:1173-1182). The independent variable must affect the mediator. The independent variable must affect the dependent variable. The mediator must have a significant effect on the dependent variable. When the mediator is included in the regression along with the independent variable, the regression coefficient (Beta value) of the independent variable on the dependent variable should decrease compared to the coefficient in the first equation, and the mediator should continue to have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

3.3. Measurement Tools

Organizational Culture: The measurement of organizational culture drew on the scale utilized by Karcioğlu and Timuroğlu (2004) in their study "Organizational Culture and Leadership," which was originally developed by Cameron and Quinn (1999). Sample expressions from the scale include "In this business, the leader is generally seen as a guide, helper, or developer" and "The management style of the organization is characterized by concepts such as job security, conformity, satisfaction, and stability in relationships." The reliability of the scale was calculated as .874.

Innovation Performance: The scale used for measuring innovation performance was adopted by Kurt (2010). The scale comprises 10 statements. Some of the expressions in the scale include "My organization is often a pioneer in offering new products and services to the market" and "New organizational structures are developed for the management of employees in my organization." The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for the scale items was determined as .821.

Intrapreneurship: The measurement of intrapreneurship was based on the scale developed by Naktiyok (2004) and used by Naktiyok and Kök (2006). The scale comprises 18 statements that form sub-factors related to innovation, a new venture orientation, organizational renewal, and proactiveness. Some expressions from the scale include "Implementing new human resource programs and policies to encourage innovation and creativity" and "Redefining industries to compete with frequently." The reliability of the scale was calculated as .892.

3.4. Findings

The findings about research variables, including means, standard deviations, correlation values, results of hypothesis testing, regression analysis result for hypotheses, and other findings, are summarized below.

3.4.1. Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlation Values of Research Variables

After determining the reliability of the employed scales, means and standard deviations of the data were calculated, and correlation values among the variables were examined. The means, standard deviations, and correlations among the variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations Among Variables

Variables	Means	Standard Deviations	1	2	3
1-Organizational Culture	3.7761	.41178	1		
2-Intrapreneurship	3.7538	.52638	.480**	1	
3-Innovation Performance	3.5791	.60062	.568**	.689**	1

Upon examination of participants' responses, the mean for organizational culture expressions was 3.78, the mean for intrapreneurship expressions was 3.75, and the mean for innovation performance expressions was 3.58. The standard deviations of these variables were found to be close to each other.

The relationships among variables were examined using correlation analysis. Correlation analysis is a commonly used method for exploring relationships in marketing research. Representing linear relationships, the coefficient from this analysis ranges between -1 and +1 (Nakip, 2003:244). The results of the correlation analysis indicate significant positive correlations at the 0.01 level between organizational culture and intrapreneurship (0.480), organizational culture and innovation performance (0.568), and intrapreneurship and innovation performance (0.689).

3.4.2. Testing Hypotheses

The results of the models established to test research hypotheses are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Regression Analysis Results for Hypotheses

Variables	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R2	F	Sig.F	Hypothesis Acceptance
H1: Organizational culture significantly influences innovation performance.								
Constant	.449	2.211	.028					
Organizational culture	.829	8.489	.000					
				.568	.323	72.016	.000	Accepted
H2: Organizational culture significantly influences intrapreneurship.								
Constant	1.439	4.149	.000					
Organizational culture	.613	6.717	.000					
				.480	.230	45.113	.000	Accepted
H3: Intrapreneurship significantly influences innovation performance.								
Constant	.630	2.467	.015					
Intrapreneurship	.786	11.668	.000					
				.689	.474	136.148	.000	Accepted

Firstly, the statistical validity and significance of the established models in the regression analysis were tested. After conducting an ANOVA analysis to test the validity and significance of the hypotheses, it was determined that the F-value, which measures the validity of the models, exceeded ± 1.96 for all models. Additionally, the p-value, which measures the significance of the models, was less than 0.05 for all three hypotheses. Hence, the established models, per the research objectives, were found to be statistically significant and valid hypotheses. Furthermore, the beta coefficients, representing the relationship between independent and dependent variables, indicated a relationship among the variables in the three hypotheses. Consequently, Hypotheses H1, H2, and H3 were accepted.

The previous regression analyses indicated that the first three conditions of the four-stage model proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986) were met. To determine whether the fourth condition was also met, a multiple regression analysis was conducted with the dependent variable being innovation performance and the independent variables being organizational culture and internal entrepreneurship. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3.

Based on the ANOVA analysis, since the F value measuring the validity of the hypotheses is greater than ± 1.96 and the p value measuring the significance of the hypothesis is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that the hypothesis formulated in accordance with the research objectives is statistically significant and valid.

Table 3.

Regression Analysis Results for Hypotheses

Variables	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R2	F	Sig.F	Hypothesis Acceptance
H4: The mediating role of intrapreneurship is significant in the relationship between organizational culture and innovation performance.								
Constant	.438	2.363	.015					
Organizational culture	.451	4.940	.000					
Intrapreneurship	.617	8.634	.000					
				.740	.548	90.842	.000	Accepted

To examine the effect of the mediating variable, the regression coefficients (Beta values) between the independent variable (organizational culture) and the dependent variable (innovation performance) were examined for Hypotheses H1 and H4. Accordingly, it was determined that the beta coefficient associated with H4 (0.451) is lower than the beta coefficient associated with H1 (0.829). These results suggest that organizational culture plays a mediating role in the influence of internal entrepreneurship on innovation performance.

4. CONCLUSION

Organizational culture directly influences all employees and operational practices within an organization. Thus, in today's increasingly competitive environment, organizations possessing a culture supportive of innovation gain a competitive edge. Innovation serves as a driving force for organizational survival (Afuah, 2009; Bessant, 2002; Betz, 2011), with employees being its crucial advocates. When the structure of organizational culture aligns with individuals within the institution, it is anticipated to have a positive impact on innovation performance and internal entrepreneurship within the organization. In an organizational culture where employees can express ideas without fear, where novel propositions and trials are encouraged, and where differences are respected, innovation and internal entrepreneurship are likely to thrive.

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between organizational culture and innovation performance, while also elucidating the mediating role of internal entrepreneurship. Our findings confirm the acceptance of all formulated hypotheses, which are further supported by various studies in the literature. Many researchers exploring organizational culture and innovation (Russell, 1989; Tushman & O'Reilly, 1997; Pfister, 2009; Kelley, 2010; Uzkuurt & Şen, 2012) have acknowledged the existence of this relationship. Similarly, according to Herbig and Dunphy (1998), culture profoundly impacts a society's innovation capacity. In essence, culture directly affects and shapes individuals residing within a community or organizational context.

Likewise, organizational culture supports and shapes entrepreneurial behaviors within the organization. The presence of internal entrepreneurs significantly influences organizational innovation performance. Each internal entrepreneurial activity results in a new product, idea, or innovative endeavor. According to Knight (1967), the primary outcome of internal entrepreneurial activities is new products and services. Our study aligns with the literature, yielding similar results from numerous studies supporting internal entrepreneurial activities (Adams et al., 1988; Brazeal, 1993; Gapp & Fisher, 2007).

In summary, internal entrepreneurs within organizations evaluate internal opportunities and resources, exhibit high self-responsibility, identify organizational prospects, and act upon them with the foundation provided. They feel secure within the organizational culture, allowing for experimentation without fear of potential errors. They collaborate harmoniously with the organization during decision-making processes, possessing mastery over the organization's system. Each entrepreneurial initiative internal entrepreneurs bring forth aligns with the organizational context and eventually evolves into innovation performance. Therefore, the creation of organizational culture must be designed to facilitate internal entrepreneurship by considering factors such as the environment, mission, vision, objectives, design, narratives, legends, social activities, spatial design, history, endorsed behavioral norms, hierarchical levels, philosophy, values, attitudes, beliefs, and organizational champions (Öktem et al., 2003). When these factors support entrepreneurship within the organization, the conversion of employee internal entrepreneurial activities into innovation outcomes becomes consistently achievable.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The authors confirm that the ethical policies of the journal, as noted on the journal's author guidelines page, have been adhered to.

In this study, all the rules specified to be followed within the scope of "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive" were complied with. None of the actions specified under the title of "Actions Contrary to Scientific Research and Publication Ethics", which is the second part of the directive, were not carried out.

Ethics committee permission information

Name of the committee that made the ethical approval: Anadolu University Social Sciences and Humanities Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee

Date of ethical approval decision: 03.03.2021

Ethical approval document approve number: E-54380210-050.99-43213, Ethical Committee Decision No. 58/61

Consent form information: Informed consent form (voluntary participation) was obtained from all individuals participating in the study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The study did not provide support from any organization.

GENİŞLETİLMİŞ ÖZET

20. Yüzyılın ikinci yarısında, ekonomik gelişmeler ve küreselleşmenin etkileri, işletmeleri sadece dinamik bir ortamda hayatta kalmaya zorlamakla kalmamış, aynı zamanda bilginin hızlı yayılması nedeniyle yeniliğin daha hızlı elde edilmesinden dolayı da baskı oluşturmuştur. Bu bağlamda, organizasyonlar, varlıklarını teknolojiye, müşteri taleplerine ve değişen koşullara uyum sağlayarak sürdürebilirler. Bunun başarılabilmesi için iş süreçlerine yeniliğin entegre edilmesi gerekmektedir. Yenilik, genellikle girişimcilik tanımına dahil edilen, değer yaratma merkezi olan (Vesper, 1990; Hisrich, 1986) ve yeni fikirleri teşvik eden (Schumpeter, 1934; Vesper, 1990; Sharma ve Chrisman, 1999; Kuratko ve Hodgetts, 2007) bir faktördür. Aynı zamanda kurumsal girişimcilik olarak da bilinen iç girişimcilik, çalışanların yaratıcılıklarını kullanarak organizasyon içinde yeni faaliyetler oluşturmalarını içerir. Burada, yeniliği destekleyen bir kurumsal kültürün kurulması hayati öneme sahiptir. Kurumsal kültür, tüm çalışanları doğrudan etkiler ve bilgiyi organizasyon için faydalı yenilikçi fikirlere dönüştürmeyi kolaylaştırmada ya da engel olmada rol oynar.

Kurumsal yenilik üzerine yapılan hem deneysel hem de teorik çalışmalar, kurumsal kültürün yenilik performansındaki önemli rolünü vurgulamaktadır (Robertson ve Wind, 1980; Coyne, 1986; Branen, 1991; Ahmed, 1998; Herbig ve Dunphy, 1998). Yeniliği destekleyen bir kurumsal kültür oluştururken, çalışanların genel refahını sağlayan, kariyer yolculuklarına hizmet eden ve kaliteli bir çalışma yaşamı sunan bir ortamın kurulması önemlidir. Bu tür bir ortam, çalışanların güçlendirilmesini ve katılımını teşvik eder. Yenilik temelde işletmeler için fikir ve kavramların ticarileştirilmesini içerir. Çalışanları ve yaratıcılıklarını teşvik eden bir kültürün yeniliği kolaylaştırdığı söylenebilir (Mumford, 2000).

Stratejilerin yenilikle ilgili olarak oluşturulması sürecinde, organizasyonlar bir dizi hedefe ulaşmayı amaçlamaktadır. Bu hedefler, rakipleri büyüme ve karlılık konusunda aşma (Crespell ve Hansen, 2008), yeni pazarları keşfetme, büyümeyi sürdürme, mevcut gelirleri koruma (Van de Vrande et al., 2009), rekabet avantajını koruma (Tushman ve Anderson, 1986; Cui et al., 2006) ve nihayetinde çeşitli yönlerde üstün sonuçlar elde etme gibi unsurları içermektedir.

İşletmeler için rekabet avantajı, yenilikle ilgili olarak öncelikli hedeflerden biridir. Yenilik stratejileri aracılığıyla, organizasyonlar pazarda liderlik elde edebilir ve çeşitli hedeflere ulaşabilirler. Daha önce belirtilen avantajların yanı sıra, yenilik faaliyetleri aynı zamanda müşteri ihtiyaçlarını karşılamada, müşteri sadakatini ve memnuniyetini artırmada ve yeni iş fırsatları yaratmada da avantajlar sunmaktadır. Bu avantajlar bireyler için enerjik ve yaratıcı çalışma ortamları oluşturmaya yöneliktir. Araştırmacılar, son zamanlarda örgütsel bağlamda çeşitli yenilik türlerinin organizasyonun uzun vadeli hayatta kalma, performans ve karlılığı üzerindeki etkilerini tartışmışlardır.

İç girişimcilik, kurulmuş bir organizasyon içinde yeni girişimler oluşturmak olarak geniş bir şekilde tanımlanabilir (Antoncic ve Hisrich, 2001). Zahra (1991:260), iç girişimciliği "kurumsal girişimcilik" terimi altında benzer bir tanımla sunarak, organizasyonun, departmanın, fonksiyonun ve proje düzeyinde ürün ve süreçlerde yenilikler ve pazar geliştirmeye yönelik hem resmi hem de gayri resmi faaliyetleri ifade etmiş ve bu faaliyetlerin organizasyonun rekabet pozisyonunu ve finansal performansını iyileştirmeye yönelik olduğunu belirtmiştir. Yaratıcılık ve yenilik genellikle iç girişimciliğin odak noktaları olarak görülmektedir. Özellikle iç girişimciler, organizasyon içinde yenilikçi fikirleri başlatan ve oluşturan bireylerdir. Knight'a (1967) göre, iç girişimcilik faaliyetlerinin en önemli sonucu yeni ürünler ve hizmetlerdir. Bu öncül temel üzerine, birçok çalışma, organizasyon içindeki iç girişimcileri desteklemenin ve beslemenin, stratejilere olumlu bir şekilde etki etme potansiyeline sahip olduklarını, değişen koşullara yaratıcı bir şekilde adapte olma yeteneklerini ve önemli örgütsel değişiklikleri tetikleme yeteneklerini tanıyarak savunmaktadır.

İç girişimciler, yenilikçilik ve uygulama kapasiteleri ile organizasyonun çevresini şekillendirme ve dolayısıyla performansını belirlemede etkili olurlar. İç girişimcilik ile kurumsal kültür arasındaki bu dinamik etkileşim, yenilikçi performans potansiyelini ortaya çıkarır. Dolayısıyla, özellikle iç girişimciliğin örgütsel yenilik performansı üzerindeki etkisi önemli olarak kabul edilebilir.

Bu çalışmanın amacı, örgüt kültürü ile yenilik performansı arasındaki ilişkiyi keşfetmek ve aynı zamanda iç girişimciliğin aracılık rolünü aydınlatmaktır. Bu bağlamda, hipotezler ve araştırma modeli aşağıdaki gibidir:

H1: Örgüt kültürünün inovasyon performansı üzerinde etkisi vardır.

H2: Örgüt kültürünün iç girişimcilik üzerinde etkisi vardır.

H3: İç girişimciliğin inovasyon performansı üzerinde etkisi vardır.

H4: Örgüt kültürünün inovasyon performansı üzerindeki etkisinde iç girişimciliğin aracılık rolü vardır.

Bu çalışmada kullanılan veriler, Türkiye'nin Kayseri ilinde faaliyet gösteren büyük bir şirketin orta ve üst düzey yöneticilerine ve beyaz yakalı çalışanlarına yöneltilen anketler aracılığıyla elde edilmiştir. Kullanılan ölçeklerin güvenilirliği onaylandıktan sonra, veri dağılımı çarpıklık ve basıklık değerlerini değerlendirerek normal dağılım açısından incelenmiştir. Hipotez testi için Baron ve Kenny'nin (1986) dört aşamalı modelini takip eden regresyon analizi kullanılmıştır. Çalışmada kullanılan ölçeklerin güvenilirliği sağlandıktan sonra, verinin ortalama ve standart sapma değerleri hesaplanmış ve değişkenler arasındaki korelasyon değerleri incelenmiştir. Katılımcı yanıtlarına dayanarak, örgüt kültürü, iç girişimcilik ve yenilik performansı için sırasıyla ortalama puanların 3.78, 3.75 ve 3.58 olduğu ve standart sapmalarının birbirine oldukça yakın olduğu belirlenmiştir. Değişkenler arasındaki ilişkileri belirlemek için korelasyon analizi kullanılmıştır. Sonuçlar, örgüt kültürü ile iç girişimcilik arasında (0.480), örgüt kültürü ile yenilik performansı arasında (0.568) ve iç girişimcilik ile yenilik performansı arasında (0.689) anlamlı pozitif korelasyonları ($p < 0.01$) göstermiştir. Regresyon analizinde, hipotezlerin geçerliliği ve anlamlılığı öncelikle bağımsız değişkenler ile bağımlı değişkenler arasındaki ilişki düzeylerini gösteren beta katsayılarını inceleyerek test edildi. Bulgular, tüm üç hipotezde de değişkenler arasında pozitif bir ilişki olduğunu göstermiş ve bu da H1, H2 ve H3'ün kabul edilmesine yol açmıştır. Önceki regresyon analizleri, Baron ve Kenny'nin (1986) dört aşamalı modelinin ilk üç koşulunun sağlandığını doğruladı. Dördüncü koşulun karşılanıp karşılanmadığını belirlemek için, bağımlı değişkenin yenilik performansı olduğu ve bağımsız değişkenlerin örgüt kültürü ve iç girişimcilik olduğu bir çoklu regresyon analizi gerçekleştirildi. ANOVA analizi sonuçları, hipotezlerin geçerliliğini ölçen F değerinin ± 1.96 'dan büyük olduğunu ve hipotezlerin anlamlılığını ölçen p değerinin 0.05'ten küçük olduğunu gösterdi. Bu nedenle, araştırma hedefleri doğrultusunda, hipotezin istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve geçerli olduğu belirlendi. Aracılık etkisini incelemek için, bağımsız değişken (örgüt kültürü) ile bağımlı değişken (yenilik performansı) arasındaki regresyon katsayıları (beta değerleri), bağımsız değişken (örgüt kültürü) ile aracı değişken (iç girişimcilik) arasındaki katsayılarla karşılaştırıldı. Bu bağlamda, H4 için beta katsayısı (0.451), H1 için beta katsayısından (0.829) daha düşük bulundu. Bu, iç girişimciliğin örgüt kültürü ile yenilik performansı arasındaki ilişkide aracı bir rol oynadığını göstermektedir.

Sonuç olarak, organizasyonlardaki iç girişimciler, organizasyon içindeki içsel fırsatları ve kaynakları değerlendiren bireylerdir. Yüksek düzeyde öz sorumluluk sergilerler, içsel fırsatları tanırlar ve bunlara dayalı olarak harekete geçebilirler. Örgüt kültürü içinde güvende hissederler, özellikle potansiyel hatalarla karşılaştıklarında ve organizasyonun karar alma süreçlerinde fonksiyon göstermeleri için yetkilendirilmişlerdir. Organizasyonun sistemini ustaca bilmelerinin yanı sıra onunla uyum içinde hareket etme yeteneğine sahiptirler. Bu iç girişimciler, organizasyon içinde girişimleri başlatırlar ki bunlar örgütsel bağlamına göre şekillenir ve nihayetinde yenilikçi performansa dönüşür. Bu nedenle, örgüt kültürünün oluşturulmasında, Öktem vd. (2003) tarafından tartışıldığı gibi, çevresel faktörler, misyon, vizyon, hedefler, tasarım, organizasyon içinde yaratılan hikayeler ve efsaneler, organizasyon tarafından teşvik edilen sosyal etkinlikler ve ortamlar, mekânsal tasarımlar, tarih, organizasyon içinde benimsenen davranış kalıpları, hiyerarşik yapı, felsefe, değerler, tutumlar, inançlar ve organizasyon değerlerini vurgulayan kahraman figürler gibi faktörler, iç girişimciliğin büyümesini teşvik edecek şekilde tasarlanmalıdır. Bu faktörler, organizasyon içinde girişimcilik desteği için uygun olduğunda, çalışanların iç girişimci faaliyetlerinin sürekli olarak yeniliğe dönüşmesi mümkün olacaktır.